

Differences in mortality in critically ill elderly patients during the second COVID-19 surge in Europe

Christian Jung (1) Christian.jung@med.uni-duesseldorf.de ,

Jesper Fjølner (2) jespfjoe@rm.dk ,

Raphael Romano Bruno (1) Raphael.Bruno@med.uni-duesseldorf.de ,

Bernhard Wernly (3) b.wernly@salk.at ,

Antonio Artigas (4) AArtigas@tauli.cat ,

Bernardo Bollen Pinto (5) Bernardo.BollenPinto@hcuge.ch ,

Joerg C. Schefold (6) joerg.schefold@insel.ch ,

Georg Wolff (1) Georg.wolff@med.uni-duesseldorf.de ,

Malte Kelm (1) malte.kelm@med.uni-duesseldorf.de ,

Michael Beil (7) beil@doctors.org.uk ,

Sviri Sigal (7) Sigals1@hadassah.org.il ,

Peter Vernon van Heerden (8) vernon@hadassah.org.il ,

Wojciech Szczeklik (9) wojciech.szczeklik@uj.edu.pl ,

Mirosław Czuczwar (10) czuczwarm@gmail.com ,

Michael Joannidis (11) michael.joannidis@tirol-kliniken.at ,

Sandra Oeyen (12) sandra.oeyen@ugent.be ,

Tilemachos Zafeiridis (13) tilemachos@hotmail.com ,

Finn H. Andersen (14) Finn.H.Andersen@helse-mr.no ,

Rui Moreno (15) r.moreno@mail.telepac.pt ,

Susannah Leaver (16) susannahleaver@nhs.net ,

Ariane Boumendil (17) ariane.boumendil@gmail.com ,

Dylan W. De Lange (18) D.W.deLange-3@umcutrecht.nl ,

Bertrand Guidet (17) bertrand.guidet@aphp.fr ,

Hans Flaatten (19) Hans.Flaatten@uib.no ,

COVIP study group (see appendix 1, covip@med.uni-duesseldorf.de)

Affiliations

1. Heinrich-Heine-University Duesseldorf, Medical Faculty, Department of Cardiology, Pulmonology and Vascular Medicine, Duesseldorf, Germany
2. Department of Intensive Care, Aarhus University Hospital, Aarhus, Denmark
3. Department of Cardiology, Paracelsus Medical University, Salzburg, Austria
4. Department of Intensive Care Medicine, CIBER Enfermedades Respiratorias, Corporacion Sanitaria Universitaria Parc Tauli, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Sabadell, Spain
5. Department of Acute Medicine, Geneva University Hospitals, Geneva, Switzerland
6. Department of Intensive Care Medicine, Inselspital, Universitätsspital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
7. Department of Medical Intensive Care, Hadassah University Medical Center, Jerusalem, Israel
8. General Intensive Care Unit, Hadassah University Medical Center, Jerusalem, Israel
9. Center for Intensive Care and Perioperative Medicine, Jagiellonian University Medical College, Krakow, Poland
10. 2nd Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Medical University of Lublin, Staszica 16, 20-081, Lublin, Poland
11. Division of Intensive Care and Emergency Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine, Medical University Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria
12. Department of Intensive Care 1K12IC Ghent University Hospital, Ghent, Belgium
13. Intensive Care Unit General Hospital of Larissa, Larissa, Greece
14. Dep. Of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Ålesund Hospital, Ålesund, Norway. Dep. of Circulation and medical imaging, Norwegian university of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway
15. Unidade de Cuidados Intensivos Neurocríticos e Trauma. Hospital de São José, Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Lisboa Central, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas de Lisboa, Nova Médical School, Lisbon, Portugal
16. General Intensive care, St George's University Hospital NHS Foundation trust, London, United Kingdom
17. Sorbonne Universités, UPMC Univ Paris 06, INSERM, UMR_S 1136, Institut Pierre Louis d'Epidémiologie et de Santé Publique, Equipe: épidémiologie hospitalière qualité et organisation des soins, F-75012, Paris, France. Assistance Publique - Hôpitaux de Paris, Hôpital Saint-Antoine, service de réanimation médicale, Paris, F-75012, France
18. Department of Intensive Care Medicine, University Medical Center, University Utrecht, the Netherlands
19. Department of Clinical Medicine, University of Bergen, Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Haukeland University Hospital, Bergen, Norway

Corresponding author:

Christian Jung, M.D. PhD

Division of Cardiology, Pulmonology, and Vascular Medicine

University Duesseldorf

Moorenstraße 5, 40225 Duesseldorf, Germany

Email: christian.jung@med.uni-duesseldorf.de

Twitter: cjungMD

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

The primary aim of this study was to assess the outcome of elderly ICU patients treated during the spring and autumn COVID-19 surges in Europe.

Methods

A prospective European observation study (The COVIP study) in ICU patients aged 70 years and older admitted with COVID-19 disease from March to December 2020. An electronic Case Record Form was used to register a number of parameters including: SOFA score, Clinical Frailty Scale, comorbidities, usual ICU procedures including pharmacotherapy, limitation of care, ICU length of stay and survival at 30 days. The study was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (ID: NCT04321265).

Results

In total 2711 patients were included, 1325 from the first and 1291 from the second surge and 94 in between. Median age was 74 and 75 years in surge 1 and surge 2 respectively. SOFA score was higher in the first surge (median 6 versus 5, $p < 0.0001$). The $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ ratio at admission was higher during surge 1 and more patients received mechanical ventilation (78% versus 68%, $p < 0.0001$). More patients were given corticosteroids in surge 2 (93 vs 38%, $p < 0.0001$). 30 days survival was lower in the second surge (57.4% vs 49.3%) with adjusted HR of 1.43 (1.18-1.74).

Conclusion

An unexpected, but significant, increase in 30-day mortality was observed during the second surge in our cohort of elderly ICU patients. The reason for this is unknown, however, practice changed and this might not be supported by sufficient evidence in this elderly population with COVID-19.

Declarations

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests. JCS reports grants (full departmental disclosure) from Orion Pharma, Abbott Nutrition International, B. Braun Medical AG, CSEM AG, Edwards Lifesciences Services GmbH, Kenta Biotech Ltd, Maquet Critical Care AB, Omnicare Clinical Research AG, Nestle, Pierre Fabre Pharma AG, Pfizer , Bard Medica S.A., Abbott AG, Anandic Medical Systems, Pan Gas AG Healthcare, Bracco, Hamilton Medical AG, Fresenius Kabi, Getinge Group Maquet AG, Dräger AG, Teleflex Medical GmbH, Glaxo Smith Kline, Merck Sharp and Dohme AG, Eli Lilly and Company, Baxter, Astellas, Astra Zeneca, CSL Behring, Novartis, Covidien, Philips Medical, Phagenesis Ltd, Prolong Pharmaceuticals and Nycomed outside the submitted work. The money went into departmental funds. No personal financial gain applied.

Availability of data

Individual participant data that underlie the results reported in this article are available to investigators whose proposed use of the data has been approved by the COVIP steering committee.

Take-home-message

Admission characteristics and management of elderly European ICU patients changed in the second surge of the pandemic and survival was lower compared to the first surge of the pandemic.

Tweet

Increased mortality during the second surge of the pandemic in critically ill elderly patients.

Preprint not peer reviewed

INTRODUCTION

The first surge of the COVID-19 pandemic between March and May 2020 affected the elderly population disproportionately. Elderly patients were overrepresented both among ICU admissions and among non-survivors¹. The hospital mortality in all patients was observed to be around 40-50%, but a higher mortality was seen in the elderly and frail population.^{2,3}

Thus, a robust prognostic stratification of elderly patients, many of whom had multiple co-morbidities, posed significant challenges in a disease which had not previously been encountered. In addition to established and new disease severity scores, geriatric characteristics notably frailty, co-morbidity and functional status, were soon confirmed to be important prognosticators in elderly COVID-19 patients³⁻⁶. Clinical studies were quickly established focusing on potential novel treatments and the management of patients with COVID-19. These included respiratory management, such as the role of mechanical ventilation and proning as well as pharmacological treatment (e.g. corticosteroids, anticoagulation and anti-inflammatory agents)⁷.

During the summer months of 2020, the spread of the virus declined. However, it became evident by early autumn that a second surge of the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic was imminent⁸. By contrast to the first surge, health care systems had now acquired an increased understanding of this disease. The pathophysiology of COVID-19 disease was described, and it was possible to predict the epidemiology of the disease based on modelling from the previous surge. Furthermore, at least theoretically, "test, track and isolate" was in operation and more robust measures such as „shielding” vulnerable individuals such as the elderly and frail were in place⁹.

The aim of this study was to assess the impact of the 'learning curve' from the first surge on patient outcomes in the second surge. In particular, whether new approaches to managing critically ill patients, both before and after admission to the ICU, had an effect on mortality.

METHODS

Design and setting

The study is a prospective observational multi-centre study of COVID-19 patients aged 70 years and older admitted to ICUs in Europe, the COVIP study. Recruitment took place from March 19th to December 31st, 2020 (A list of collaborators is shown in supplemental material 1. A map of participating ICUs is shown in supplemental material 2. Recruitment in countries over the three different time periods is shown in supplemental material 3). The study was organised by the Very old Intensive care Patients (VIP) project ^{10,11} within the European Society of Intensive Care Medicine (ESICM) who also endorsed the study (www.vipstudy.org). National coordinators were responsible for the recruitment of ICUs and for obtaining national and local ethical permission. In addition, national coordinators supervised patient recruitment. Due to variations in requirement for ethical consent, some countries could recruit patients without upfront informed consent while others had to obtain it. The study deliberately allowed for co-enrolment of study patients to other COVID-19 studies. The study was registered on ClinicalTrials.gov (ID: NCT04321265) and adhered to the European Union General Data Privacy Regulation (GDPR) directive.

Study preparation started during the first phase of the pandemic and recruitment commenced on March 19th 2020. Throughout the pandemic recruitment to the COVIP study was monitored by weekly virtual steering group meetings. The first recruitment period, representing the first surge of the pandemic, was defined from 19th of March until 26th of May and the second recruitment period, reflecting the second surge, from September 1st to December 31st. This was also reflected by the number of ICU patients published by international registries. Patients recruited between these two recruitment periods were considered to be admitted outside a specific surge of the pandemic. Each participating ICU included consecutive patients. A diagnosis of COVID-19 was made based on a positive polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test. Patients were followed up until death, the primary endpoint was survival at 30 days.

Study population

Eligible patients were 70 years or older with a proven diagnosis of COVID-19 and admitted to an intensive care unit (ICU). Pre-ICU triage was not part of this study. To avoid duplication caused by the transfer of a patient from one ICU to another, each patient could only be entered once into the database regardless of readmission, transfer or other reason. This resulted in a unique electronic database record for each patient. The reference date was day 1 of the first admission to an ICU. All consecutive days were numbered sequentially from the day of admission. To limit bias in the comparison of the two surges, only patients admitted to European ICUs that recruited patients during both surges were included in the analysis. (supplemental material 4).

Data collection

Centres collected data using the online CRF. Day one sequential organ-failure assessment (SOFA) score on admission was calculated either manually or using an online calculator in the electronic CRF as described previously^{10,11}. The PaO₂/FIO₂ index (pO₂/FiO₂-ratio) on admission was calculated using the pO₂ [mmHg] and the F_iO₂ [%] from the first arterial blood gas. ICU length of stay (LOS) was recorded in hours. As described previously,¹⁰ the electronic CRF and database ran on a secure server set up by and stored at Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark.

Frailty, comorbidities and organ support

The frailty level prior to the acute illness and hospital admission was assessed using the Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS) as published previously¹¹. A detailed definition of comorbidities and organ support can be found in supplemental material 5.

Outcome measurement

The primary endpoint was the survival-status assessed at 30 days after ICU admission. Data could be retrieved either directly, from the hospital administration system or following telephone follow-up. Limitation of life-sustaining therapies such as withholding or withdrawing organ support was documented ¹².

Statistical analysis

Baseline characteristics of patients were analysed as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and as medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs) for continuous variables. Comparisons between the three periods were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis test (ANOVA) for continuous variables and the χ^2 or Fisher exact test for categorical variables as appropriate. Comparisons between surges and the time between the surges respectively were evaluated using the Wilcoxon test for continuous variables and the χ^2 or Fisher exact test for categorical variables as appropriate. Bonferroni correction was used to adjust for multiple comparisons. Variables for all adjusted analyses were age, sex, SOFA, PaO₂/FIO₂, frailty, BMI, habitat and comorbidities (definition in supplemental material 5).

The crude overall survival at 30 days after ICU admission was estimated by the Kaplan-Meier method and compared using a log-rank test. All patients were censored at day 30. The 30-day survival adjusted for baseline characteristics was estimated using a Cox model. Adjusted survival curves were produced using an inverse probability-weighted Kaplan-Meier estimation. Significance was tested using a Cox regression model weighted by the same weights (inverse probability-weighted Cox). We first estimated our models on the complete data set and then used multiple imputation for participants with missing data, using predictive mean matching for continuous variables, logistic regression for binary data, and polytomous regression for (unordered) categorical data.

Incidence of organ support and treatment limitation were estimated using cumulative incidence analysis considering ICU death and ICU discharge as competing risks. Univariate comparisons were performed using Gray's test.

All p values were two-sided, and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed with R 3.2.3 software packages (R Development Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

RESULTS

As illustrated in Table 1, 2711 patients from European countries were included in the COVIP study during the different time periods. There were nearly equal numbers of patients recruited during the first and the second surge of the pandemic. During these two surges, patient characteristics changed with slightly increasing age, body mass index, CFS and SOFA score. In addition, PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio was lower in patients during the second surge of the pandemic and there was an increased prevalence of diabetes mellitus and ischemic heart disease.

For additional comparison, patients recruited in the time frame between the two surges were analysed and exhibited some differences in characteristics perhaps revealing a different management prior to ICU admission as illustrated by lower CFS.

During the second surge of the pandemic, management had changed when compared with the first surge of the pandemic (Table 2). Patients were intubated for mechanical ventilation less frequently and if mechanical ventilation was performed, intubation took place later. By contrast, non-invasive ventilation was performed more often. Prone positioning was equivalent during both periods. Renal replacement therapy and treatment with vasoactive substances was performed less frequently. This is also illustrated by the time-to-event analysis as outlined in Figure 1. Treatment with antibiotics decreased, while the treatment with corticosteroids increased. Of note, there was no difference in withholding or withdrawal of treatment.

We observed a lower rate of survival in the second surge of the pandemic (Figure 2). This finding was supported by a model comparing survival adjusted for age, sex, SOFA, CFS, BMI, and comorbidities (Table 3). Missing values were imputed and the model constructed

again confirmed previous findings (supplementary material 6). In addition, this has been confirmed by several sensitivity analyses for survival analysis (supplemental material 7) and the adjusted survival models (model 2: patients' age >75: HR 1.35 (95%CI: 1.12-1.62); patients with diabetes mellitus: HR 1.32 (95%CI: 1.06-1.64); patients receiving mechanical ventilation: HR 1.45 (95%CI: 1.21-1.73).

DISCUSSION

In this study of patients aged 70 and above admitted with COVID-19 disease, we found a decrease in thirty day survival from 57.4% in the first surge to 49.3% in the second surge, even after adjustment for important co-factors such as age, gender, SOFA score, comorbidities and frailty. The major differences between the two groups besides mortality were the reduction in the use of intubation and mechanical ventilation, reduced use of vasoactive drugs, increased use of non-invasive ventilation (NIV) and an increased use of corticosteroids during the second surge.

These findings are surprising, as the ICU community had used their experience from treating these patients during the first surge. Here the initial very high reported¹³ mortality was soon followed with a reduction in mortality towards the end of the first surge¹⁴. It was thought that in the second surge, the use of steroids in patients with severe respiratory distress, and the delay in intubation, following the use of NIV to its full potential would translate in better outcomes.

To date, there are only a few reports comparing the two surges in COVID-19 hospitalised patients. In a study from 955 US hospitals, researchers compared a trend analysis for the first surge: from Jan 1st to April 30th and May 1st to June 30th. The overall hospital event rate for 30 day mortality or referral to hospice within 30 days fell from 16.56% to 9.29%, indicating improved outcome in the last period of the first surge suggesting a steep learning curve¹⁵. This has also been confirmed by a study from the UK in >21,000 critical care patients

with COVID-19 showing improved survival from March to June 2020 ¹⁶. In another study looking at COVID-19 outcomes in hospitalised patients with rheumatic disease, outcomes from the first 90 days were compared to the following 90 days ¹⁷. They found a reduced risk of hospitalisation and admission to an ICU in the late cohort, and also a fall in the risk of death (9.3% versus 4.5%).

Our patients were all treated in the ICU during both surges and therefore a comparison with these initial experiences from other patient groups is difficult. However, reports from Intensive Care National Audit and Research Centre (ICNARC) in UK reveals valuable information in this respect. This national registry compared patients admitted before and after September 1st, 2020 and found a small difference in mortality from 47.7% in the first to 47.1% in the second cohort ¹⁸. However, 22% of their patients were still in hospital, so the final mortality rate may change significantly. Their results were also similar to our patient cohort in other aspects with considerably fewer patients receiving mechanical ventilation, (down from 72 to 50%) and more patients given basic respiratory support (from 25 to 47%). In addition, the duration of mechanical ventilation was shorter. Analogous to our results they found that more patients had a low PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio at admission.

There are several possible reasons for the increased mortality seen in our study. While our data does not give a satisfactory explanation, it allows for several potential contributing factors to be discussed.

A worse outcome might have been caused by the increased length of time spent in other departments before ICU admission, resulting in patients deteriorating prior to eventual admission. This is supported by a decreased PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio seen at ICU admission in the second period, possibly suggesting more severe respiratory failure. This combined with a trend towards a reduction in the use of mechanical ventilation may not have been beneficial in this group of elderly critically ill patients. A similar rate of limitation of life sustaining therapy was seen in the two cohorts, so this is unlikely to account for the difference in mortality. Two

additional differences are a slight increase in age and frailty score in the second cohort, which could explain an increase in mortality, however the difference in mortality remained after adjustment for these factors.

Another possible explanation for the increased mortality, which cannot be ruled out, could be a reduction in quality of care, despite all dedicated efforts on the part of the staff, in the second compared to the first surge. When the second surge started, many hospitals and in particular ICUs had already been over stretched for half a year and were running well above their usual capacity. This had consequences for both the permanent staff who had been working increased hours over a long period of time, and also the continuous dilution of expertise as non-ICU personnel, both physicians and nurses were being brought in to work in ICUs. There has been great concern about the burden of work on the health of ICU workers¹⁹, leading to fatigue and physical and mental health problems, which ultimately may affect quality of care. In the current survival analysis, it seems that survival differs from day 14 onwards and it is tempting to speculate that quality of care in particular, had consequences for elderly patients with prolonged treatment duration.

Another important factor may be related to use of corticosteroids. In the second surge, 93% of our patients received corticosteroids, which is more than twice that found in the first cohort. It is well documented that steroids have potentially serious side-effects in ICU patients. Steroids increase infection rate and hence mortality in patients admitted with influenza pneumonia²⁰ and thus could also increase the number of patients acquiring sepsis in the ICU. In a recent retrospective study of 294 critically ill patients with COVID-19, steroids significantly increased mortality if given within three days of ICU admission²¹. This study also found an increased number of secondary infections in the corticosteroid group. It was of interest to study the details in the supplementary appendix from the Recovery study where COVID-19 patients were randomised to receive corticosteroids⁷. Only a small number of patients requiring mechanical ventilation were over 70 years old; 55 patients in the dexamethasone group and 114 in the usual care group. In a pre-specified analysis of the Recovery trial, there was no

difference in mortality in patients above 70 years. Despite this, this landmark trial – among others – changed guidelines²² and practice independent of age, in severely ill COVID-19 patients. The practice of corticosteroid use is only supported by a small open non-randomised study of non-ICU treated elderly COVID-19 patients from France²¹. Although the Recovery trial is a major achievement in these difficult times, some unanswered questions remained, for example, it was unclear whether patients with uncontrolled diabetes, acute delirium, underlying malignancy, immunosuppression, or other conditions in which corticosteroids might have harmful effects were included²³. These clinical circumstances are frequently seen in elderly patients. In our ICU cohort, a third of the patients had established diabetes mellitus. Waterer and Rello have recently suggested a more targeted approach to the use of steroids in COVID-19 patients, rather than a single uniform strategy for all ICU patients. This included patients over the age of 70 years as well as those with diabetes mellitus²⁴.

Finally, development of COVID-19 mutations may change virulence and hence potentially lead to worse outcomes. It is well known that during the pandemic a new mutant virus emerged in Europe²⁵. The clinical properties of this new strain are largely unknown as whole genome sequence studies have not been performed in large scale and ordinary COVID-19 testing does not differentiate mutant viruses from the original one. Such a cause for worse outcomes is uncertain but remains a theoretical possibility.

Our study has some weaknesses mainly concerning the absence of details of variables that might account for our differences in outcome. There was no information about how steroids were administered, no control group of younger COVID-19 patients for comparison, the pre-ICU treatment and triage were not known and there was no information about quality of care and the nurse-to-patient ratios. However, we have observed that an untargeted but consistent change in practice has changed the outcomes between the cohorts in the two surges.

Conclusion

This is the first study in critically ill elderly patients with COVID-19 infection that compares mortality data between the first and second surges of the pandemic. We have found an unexpected but significant rise in mortality in elderly COVID-19 patients treated in the ICU during the second surge. The cause of this rise is unknown but possible explanations have been discussed. Our main concern is whether the widespread changes in practice and treatment of COVID-19 between the two surges have caused this increased mortality in elderly patients. Further studies are urgently warranted to provide more evidence.

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Figure legends

Figure 1: Cumulative incidences for (A) mechanical ventilation (MV), (B) non-invasive ventilation (NIV), (C) combined MV and NIV, (D) vasoactive drugs, (E) renal replacement therapy (RRT), and (F) treatment limitation during the first and the second surge and the time period between the two surges.

Figure 2: Kaplan-Meier-curve until 30 days for patients admitted during the first and the second surge and the time period between the two surges.

Table legends

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population across the three time periods of the study.

Table 2: Management of patients during the first and second surge of the pandemic

Table 3: Adjusted survival model using the first surge of the pandemic as reference

Table 1

	First surge (until May 26th 2020)	Between first and second surge May 27 th – August 31 st 2020	Second surge September 1 st – December 31 st 2020	p-value First surge versus between first/second surge	p-value First surge versus second surge
Patients (n)	1325	94	1291		
Characteristics					
Age (years)	74 (72-78)	74 (71-78)	75 (72-79)	0.24	0.02 (*)
Sex (male sex)	74%	74%	70%	1	0.11
Weight (kg)	80 (72-90)	83 (75-91)	80 (72-91)	0.12	0.33
Height (cm)	170 (165-177)	170 (165-175)	170 (164-177)	0.43	0.11
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.5 (24.7-30.1)	28.9 (25.7-31.2)	27.6 (24.9-31.1)	0.03 (*)	0.03 (*)
Clinical status					
CFS	3 (2-4)	2 (2-3)	3 (2-4)	0.01 (*)	0.01 (*)
SOFA	6 (3-8)	6 (4-8)	5 (3-7)	0.48	<0.0001 (***)
PAO ₂ /FIO ₂	125 (84-181)	94 (68-152)	104 (75-156)	0.004	<0.0001 (***)
Comorbidities					
Diabetes mellitus, (%)	31%	24%	36%	0.20	0.0084 (**)
Ischemic heart disease, (%)	20%	21%	25%	0.85	0.0004 (***)
Chronic kidney disease, (%)	15%	12%	17%	0.60	0.22
Arterial hypertension, (%)	66%	63%	67%	0.61	0.50
Chronic pulmonary disease, (%)	22%	17%	23%	0.31	0.49
Chronic heart failure, (%)	14%	13%	15%	0.79	0.67

Table 2

	First surge (until May 26th 2020)	Second surge September 1 st – December 31 st 2020	p-value
Patients (n)	1325	1291	
Time periods			
Days with symptoms prior to hospital admission	7 (4-10)	7 (4-10)	0.33
Days in the hospital prior to ICU admission	2 (1-4)	2 (1-5)	<0.0001
Length of ICU stay for patients discharged alive (days)	15 (6-29)	9 (5-19)	<0.0001
Respiratory management			
Mechanical ventilation started on day 1	58%	42%	<0.0001
Mechanical ventilation Cumulative incidence at day 15 Cumulative incidence at day 30	78% (76-80) 78% (76-80)	68% (65-70) 68% (65-71)	<0.0001
Non-invasive ventilation Cumulative incidence at day 15 Cumulative incidence at day 30	19% (16-21) 21% (19-23)	27% (24-29) 28% (25-30)	<0.0001
Non-invasive or mechanical ventilation Cumulative incidence at day 15 Cumulative incidence at day 30	85% (83-86) 85% (83-87)	79% (76-81) 79% (77-81)	<0.0001
Prone positioning Cumulative incidence at day 15 Cumulative incidence at day 30	57% (54-60) 58% (54-61)	55% (52-59) 56% (53-60)	0.57
Further management			
Vasoactive drugs	77%	67%	<0.0001
Renal replacement therapy	18%	14%	0.0043
Corticosteroids	38%	93%	<0.0001
Antibiotics	92%	88%	0.0007
Withholding or Withdrawal of treatment modalities Cumulative incidence at day 15 Cumulative incidence at day 30	29% (27-32) 37% (35-40)	30% (27-32) 37% (35-40)	0.86

Table 3

	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
15 days survival	71.2% (95% CI 68.8-73.7)	68.5% (95% CI 59.6-78.7)	68.6% (95% CI 66.1-71.3)
30 days survival	57.4% (95% CI 54.8-60.2)	57.4% (95% CI 48.1-68.5)	49.3% (95% CI 46.6-52.2)
Unadjusted HR	Ref.	HR 1.00 (0.69-1.44)	HR 1.37 (1.14-1.65)
Adjustment 1*	Ref.	HR 1.04 (0.69-1.57)	HR 1.43 (1.19-1.71)
Adjustment 2**	Ref.	HR 1.04 (0.68-1.60)	HR 1.43 (1.18-1.74)

* age, sex, SOFA, PAO₂/FIO₂, frailty, BMI, (N = 2130 observations)

** age, sex, SOFA, PAO₂/FIO₂, frailty, BMI, comorbidities (N = 2078 observations)

No. at risk

	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
First surge	1315	1205	1052	948	866	792	753
Between	92	81	72	63	55	55	53
Second surge	1250	1146	1003	857	743	664	606